

NOMINATIVE SENTENCES IN LANGUAGES WITH DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

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Annotation. *The article is dedicated to nominative sentences in various languages, Mari and German. Nominative sentences in these languages are far and wide and are significant syntactic means for accomplishment of discourse correspondence. In the concentrated on languages the issue of the chief pieces of the nominative sentence and of the standards of their separation from different sorts of mononuclear sentences is contrastingly settled, and importance of exploration is characterized by it. The motivation behind work is to break down design, semantics and working of nominative sentences in the languages connecting with various phonetic gatherings. To accomplish this reason one should uncover the quintessence of nominative sentences in the broke down languages, their characterization and separation from different kinds of mononuclear sentences, working in the discourse.*

Keywords: *mononuclear sentence, nominative sentence, principal part, principles of differentiation, prevalence, context, interference.*

Introduction. Nominative sentence is a broad sort of sentence in the language. It is a significant syntactic method for accomplishment of discourse correspondence. Mari and German have a place with various gatherings of languages. The Mari language is illustrative of the Finno-Ugric gathering of languages, which is the most seasoned on the planet. The German language is the language of the German gathering. These days the relative typological investigation of languages of various gatherings stirs extensive interest of researchers according to a hypothetical perspective. In any case the functional side of this issue is likewise significant. In showing a foreign language instructor genuinely should depend on the information on the local language. This way is a way to progress. In the concentrated on languages the issue of the chief pieces of the nominative sentence and of the standards of their separation from different sorts of mononuclear sentences is diversely settled, and pertinence of research is characterized by it. The motivation behind work is to investigate construction, semantics and working of nominative sentences in the languages connecting with

various etymological gatherings. To accomplish this reason one should uncover the pith of nominative sentences in the broke down languages, their characterization and separation from different kinds of mononuclear sentences, working in the discourse. Considering the nominative sentences in the work it is utilized the strategy for synchronous depictions of the gathered material utilizing the distributive investigation and the diachronic components of the strategy, the similar technique permits laying out likenesses and contrasts in the examined languages. Nominative sentences have a place with the classification mononuclear sentences and its primary part signifies the presence, the presence of subject or peculiarity in right now or immortal. Examination of genuine material of the German and the Mari languages permits to express that this kind of sentences is far and wide both in the German and Mari languages. The fundamental element of the nominative sentences is an articulation as nominative grammatical form in the nominative case, and the assignment of subjects or peculiarities of the real world. In the Mari language nominative sentence as one of the assortments of mononuclear sentences is portrayed in the exploration works of L. P. Vasikova and V. T. Timofeeva. ^[1]

The two researchers have the very assessment that such sentence demonstrates the subjects and the peculiarities of regular day to day existence, and they have one primary part communicated as nominative grammatical form, Шыже. Изи лум мландым леведын. 'Pre-winter. Snow covered the ground'. Комбо-Шүргө чодыра... Йүлем пасу. Тышак икияш шурно ўдышашлык. 'Combo Shyurgo woods... worn out field. There they ought to be planted'. L. P. Vasikova noticed that in the Mari language a few hardships in recognizing of the nominative and fragmented sentences emerge. As per the analyst in concluding this question it is important to depend on the specific circumstance, which gives more complete data which is essential for understanding the significance of the expression, for instance: Шошо. Урем кошка. 'Spring. in a real sense. Road is drying'. Шўльө сорла. Тоймаксола марий-влак кече лекме дене пырля пасу пашашке вашкат. 'Collecting of oats. With dawn Тоумаксoла Mari are in rush to the field'. Optional pieces of the sentence, specifically the property in the Mari language, L. P. Vasikova claims, influence the expansion and non-augmentation of the nominative sentences, for instance: А теве ял. Вот урем. 'Also, town here.

¹ Vasikova, L. P. (1987). The Modern Mari language. The syntax of the simple tense: The Reference for teachers / L. P. Vasikova. – Yoshkar-Ola: The Mari book publisher, 144 p.

Road here' Май пүртүс! / ... Чонлан тыгане лайык, / Ончылнет мучашдыме топа... . 'May nature! .. / It is so great for soul / Ahead It is endless field'. In the Mari language after V. T. Timofeeva 3 kinds of nominative sentences are generally recognized. The first sort is distinct, showing the normal peculiarities which happen in daily existence occasions, general setting of activity, for instance: Ял. Шочмо ял. Кеч-көлан тудо шерге. 'Town. Home town'. Индешымше май! Сеньмаш кече дене, куан кече дене тўня волгалтеш. in a real sense 'May 9! With day of triumph, the world is lit with occasion'. The subsequent sort is decisive which is utilized the illustrative molecule вот, тебе, уна, 'here', for example: тебе тумо. Тебе корно. Тебе курык, Тебе ер. Ер воктеке толын шордо, толын шордо пеш чевер. 'Here oak. Here way, here the mountain. Here the lake. Elk has come to the lake, lovely elk has come'. Nominative sentences, utilized in the names of organizations, establishments, papers, magazines, have a place with the third kind of nominative sentences, for model: М. Шкетан лўмеш Марий драматический театр. 'The Mari Drama Theater named after M. Shketana'. «ямде лий». '«Be ready»', «ончыко». '«Forward»'. V. T. Timofeeva noticed that nominative sentences depict articles and peculiarities in the current state. The nominative sentence is changed into the class of a two-part one by utilizing the previous tense, for instance: Шошо кас. 'It is spring evening'. Шошо кас ыле. 'It was spring evening'. It ought to allude composed discourse and especially writing to the field of use of nominative sentences, which is related fundamentally with a component of the construction of such sentences intended to stand out. In current German partitioning nominative sentences into 3 gatherings: sentences of being is acknowledged: (existential); expressive and ostensible sentences (http://www.multikulti.ru/Strategy/data/Strategy_info_718.html<http://www.mul> ikulti.ru/Strategy/information/Strategy_in fo_718.html). The principal bunch is made out of sentences of being (existential) portraying the peculiarities of daily existence, e.g.; 'Winter. It snows'. The subsequent gathering is addressed by the definite sentences that are much of the time utilized in the informal discourse, for instance: 'Street. The way to the satisfaction'. Ostensible sentences are remembered for the third gathering of nominative sentences, addressing the signs, the title of books, magazines. In the German language E. I. Shendels characterizes nominative sentences as ostensible ones and traits to the gathering

of mononuclear sentences. The analyst recognizes three gatherings of mononuclear sentences. [2]

The first gathering is shaped by basic sentences, the subsequent gathering comprises of exclamatory sentences. Ostensible or on the other hand nominative sentences involve the third gathering of mononuclear sentences. E. Shendels looks at that as a gathering of a thing is the primary individual from nominative sentences, and the researcher noticed that such sort of sentences «is utilized in the depiction when the creator makes the entire picture of the world for the peruser utilizing specific outlines». The researcher additionally alludes the purported stage headings to nominative sentences, for instance: 'Extraordinary room. A touch of furniture. Ways to one side and to one side'. «In current German writing ..., E. Shendels notes, ... it frequently tracks down unique syntactic gathering of seclusion of any piece of the sentence into a different sentence». This individual from the sentence accomplishes syntactic independence, and becomes mononuclear sentence. Relations, objects, verb-modifying modifiers also, predicates can frame mononuclear sentences, for instance: 'A man showed up between the chimney stack and the vent. A man in the officer's uniform, is a fighter'.

The examination of the hypothetical and the verifiable material permits to make determinations about the likenesses and contrasts of the nominative sentences in Mari and German. In the German language, as in the Mari language, the nominative sentences express just the implications of the current state. The portrayals of the occasions, conditions, items and peculiarities previously and the future, show on the binomiality of the sentence in the two languages. The Mari and German languages frequently utilize the normal kind of the nominative sentences to give more symbolism for depicting reality. As a part giving the principal individual from the nominative sentence, the attributive is many times utilized in the two languages, the primary capacity in many languages is the outflow of an assortment of the subjective and the situational attributes. In the German language, as in Mari, the field of the utilizing of the nominative sentences is the creative and, in a few different ways, editorial writing. The nominative sentences are utilized by creators as an expressive gadget, adding to the discourse symbolism and enlightening. Setting and circumstance are the fundamental

² Mononuclear nominative sentences in Russian, English and German. URL: http://www.multikulti.ru/Strategy/info/Strategy_info_718.html (date of access 10.04.16).

variables in the portion of the nominative sentences, simply because of them it is accomplished comprehension and correspondence. In the Mari and German languages, the nominative sentence is far reaching sort of the sentence. The nominative sentences, notwithstanding having a place with the various gatherings, are comparable in the approach to framing, types and capacities in discourse in these languages.

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